

Degenerate asymptotic phenomena in the buckling of inhomogeneously pre-stressed cylindrical shells

(Supplementary online material I)

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1 Introduction

The material included below complements the results reported in the main paper (henceforth referred to as CDC25*). Some of the original references from that work are listed again at the end of this note in order to make it reasonably self-contained.

In CDC25 it was shown that the dispersion function plays a central role in determining the nature of the localised solutions admitted by the model buckling system. Building on this insight, we revisit the earlier study [1] to provide further clarification on some of its findings. The precise details will become clearer as we first outline the equations that will be examined in the following sections.

The bifurcation problem addressed in [1] focused on the potential instabilities of a short, thin elastic cylinder with length L , radius R , and thickness h , subjected to pure bending. Specifically, the forces applied at both ends were statically equivalent to a moment acting in the plane of curvature of the cylinder. The analysis was based on the Donnell-Mushtari-Vlasov (DMV) shallow-shell buckling equations (e.g., see [2, 3]) formulated in terms of the transverse displacement $w \equiv w(x, \theta)$ and a stress function $F \equiv F(x, \theta)$. If $\check{\sigma}_{xx}$, $\check{\sigma}_{x\theta}$ and $\check{\sigma}_{\theta\theta}$ correspond to the distribution of pre-buckling membrane stresses in the cylinder, then the buckling equations can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} D\nabla^4 w - h \left(\check{\sigma}_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + 2\check{\sigma}_{x\theta} \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial \theta} + \check{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} \frac{1}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} \right) - \frac{h}{R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right) = 0, \\ \nabla^4 F + \frac{E}{R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

where $D \equiv Eh^3/12(1 - \nu^2)$ represents the bending rigidity, the Laplacian is defined according to $\nabla^2 := \partial_x^2 + R^{-2}\partial_\theta^2$, and $\nabla^4 := \nabla^2\nabla^2$. In [1] the cylinder was assumed to be loaded by compressive axial forces $P > 0$ and in-plane bending moments $M > 0$, while the boundary conditions were of the simply-supported type. Prior to buckling the deformation of the cylindrical shell is described by a linear membrane state of stress characterised by the in-plane stress distribution $\check{\sigma}_{xx} = -(\sigma_C + \sigma_B \cos \theta)$, $\check{\sigma}_{x\theta} = \check{\sigma}_{\theta\theta} \equiv 0$, with

$$\sigma_C \equiv \frac{P}{2\pi R h} \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_B \equiv \frac{M}{\pi R^2 h}. \quad (1.2)$$

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On substituting (1.2) into (1.1), the resulting equations turn out to be amenable to solutions with separable variables of the form

$$[w, F]^T = [G(\theta), H(\theta)]^T \sin\left(\frac{q_m x}{R}\right), \quad q_m := \frac{m\pi R}{L}, \quad (m = 1, 2, \dots), \quad (1.3)$$

where the superscript T stands for ‘transposition’; q_m represents the *axial* buckle half-wavelength, while the azimuthal amplitudes $H \equiv H(\theta)$, $G \equiv G(\theta)$ denote the new main dependent variables. Use of (1.3) in (1.1) shows that these new functions satisfy a set of two coupled fourth-order ordinary differential equations, which can be simplified further by suitable rescaling[†]

$$\bar{G} := \frac{G}{R}, \quad \bar{H} := 4\sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)}\frac{H}{ERh}, \quad \mu := \sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)}\frac{R}{h}, \quad q := \mu^{-1}q_m^2, \quad (1.4a)$$

$$\lambda_C := \frac{\sigma_C}{\sigma_*}, \quad \lambda_B := \frac{\sigma_B}{\sigma_*}, \quad \sigma_* := \frac{E}{\sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)}}\left(\frac{h}{R}\right). \quad (1.4b)$$

The normalisation term σ_* represents the theoretical *compressive buckling stress* for an infinitely long elastic cylindrical shell. In the following discussion we focus exclusively on the pure bending scenario, setting $\lambda_C = 0$ and re-labelling λ_B as λ for consistency with CDC25. Removing the bars from the re-scaled variables, the reduced bifurcation equations can then be cast in a more compact form as

$$\mathcal{L}\left(i\mu^{-1/2}\frac{d}{d\theta}, q, \lambda, \theta\right)\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u} \equiv \mathbf{u}(\theta) := [G(\theta), H(\theta)]^T, \quad (1.5)$$

where

$$\mathcal{L} \equiv \mathcal{L}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) := \begin{bmatrix} D^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) & D^{12}(q) \\ D^{21}(q) & D^{22}(p, q) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.6)$$

and

$$D^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) := (p^2 + q)^2 - 4q\lambda \cos \theta, \quad D^{12}(q) := q, \quad (1.7a)$$

$$D^{21}(q) := -4q, \quad D^{22}(p, q) := (p^2 + q)^2. \quad (1.7b)$$

One of the key goals in our previous study [1] was to explore various asymptotic simplifications of (1.5) that enable accurate approximations of the critical values of λ . Despite the relative simplicity of the equations, this task is challenging due to the dependence of the eigen-parameter on the artificially introduced quantity q_m , as defined in (1.3). Since $\lambda \equiv \lambda(q_m)$, from a practical point of view the interest lies in determining its minimum values, which, in general, can only be obtained numerically. Figure 1 provides a typical numerical example illustrating the behaviour of λ for $\mu \simeq 826$; the global minimum of the curve identifies the critical values of λ and q_m . Guided by numerical simulations of the original bifurcation equation for $\mu \gg 1$ and applying standard multiple-scale asymptotic techniques, we demonstrated that (1.5) can be reduced to second-order differential equations along the left and right branches. However, in the close vicinity of the global minimum (the round marker in Figure 1), the reduced model takes the form of a fourth-order equation. In the next section, we will use the concept of dispersion function for the system (1.5) to establish a deeper connection between the earlier findings of [1] and the nature of the stationary points of the dispersion relation.

[†]The re-scaling of H differs from that in [1], and the quantity λ_m from that reference has been re-labelled as q_m to prevent confusion with the current eigenvalue λ . Additionally, to circumvent the need for Taylor expansions at $+\infty$, we introduce the new variable q , which remains $\mathcal{O}(1)$ as $\mu \gg 1$ in the regime of interest here (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Typical *neutral stability curve* for the bifurcation system (1.5) corresponding to $R/h = 5 \times 10^2$ and $\nu = 0.3$; see (1.4a) for the definition of the asymptotic parameter μ . The round marker identifies the absolute minimum of the function $\lambda = \lambda(q)$.

2 The dispersion function

Just as in CDC25, the asymptotic structure of (1.5) in the limit $\mu \gg 1$ depends on a suitably defined *dispersion function*, which in our case corresponds to the determinant of (1.6)

$$\mathcal{D}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) := \begin{vmatrix} D^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) & D^{12}(q) \\ D^{21}(q) & D^{22}(p, q) \end{vmatrix}. \quad (2.1)$$

The equation obtained by setting this to zero, i.e.

$$\mathcal{D}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) = 0, \quad (2.2)$$

gives the *dispersion relation*. As already explained in CDC25, equation (2.2) allows us to express λ as a function of the other parameters (p , q , and θ); in particular, for the pure bending cylindrical shell problem we find

$$\Lambda(p, q, \theta) := \frac{1}{4q} \left[(p^2 + q)^2 + \frac{4q^2}{(p^2 + q)^2} \right] \frac{1}{\cos \theta}. \quad (2.3)$$

It will become clear shortly that equation (2.2) emerges in connection with the leading-order approximation of the asymptotic problem mentioned at the end of §1. For now we will be content

with examining the possible positive minima of (2.3), while keeping in mind its relation to the neutral stability curve seen in Figure 1; the following restrictions will be imposed on its independent variables,

$$p \geq 0, \quad q > 0, \quad -\pi \leq \theta < \pi. \quad (2.4)$$

The stationary points of Λ can be identified by solving

$$\Lambda_p = \Lambda_q = \Lambda_\theta = 0, \quad (2.5)$$

where the subscripts are used to indicate partial differentiation with respect to the corresponding variable (a convention that will be employed throughout this work). The final equation in (2.5) is decoupled from the other two. Its possible solutions include $\theta = \theta_0 := -\pi$ and $\theta = \theta_0 := 0$, with the former being inadmissible as it violates the initial assumption $\Lambda > 0$. As for the remaining two equations in (2.5), note that

$$\Lambda_p = 0 \implies p[(p^2 + q)^4 - 4q^2] = 0, \quad (2.6a)$$

$$\Lambda_q = 0 \implies (p^2 - q)[(p^2 + q)^4 - 4q^2] = 0. \quad (2.6b)$$

Strictly speaking, the requirement (2.6b) need only be imposed for the so-called critical case, corresponding to the absolute minimum of the response curve shown in Figure 1. For describing the asymptotics of the left and right branches, q should remain a free parameter that can be adjusted as needed.

Based on (2.6), there are a couple of options for the critical case

$$\text{Case 1: } p = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad (p^2 + q)^4 - 4q^2 = 0;$$

$$\text{Case 2: } (p^2 + q)^4 - 4q^2 = 0. \quad (2.7)$$

In the first case the solution is straightforward: $p = p_0 := 0$ and $q = q_0 := 2$; combined with the previously determined θ_0 , this gives $\Lambda(p_0, q_0, \theta_0) = 1$. The second possibility is more subtle; assuming that (p, q) satisfy the stated algebraic constraint, it is again found that $\Lambda = 1$. However, solving for p in the constraint reveals that $p^2 = \sqrt{2q} - q$. For $q = 2$ we recover the solution of the previous case, while the restriction $p^2 > 0$ shows that $0 < q < 2$. Based on the information in Figure 1, this regime is relevant to the left branch of the neutral stability curve. Furthermore, it also transpires that the right branch is described by the choice $p = 0$ and $q > 2$. It is perhaps worth emphasising that q must still remain $\mathcal{O}(1)$ on both branches of the neutral stability curve.

The key insights from the above results can be summarised as follows,

- critical case: $p = 0$, $q = 2$, and $\theta = 0$, with

$$\Lambda_p = \Lambda_{pp} = \Lambda_{ppp} = 0, \quad \Lambda_{pppp} > 0;$$

- right branch: $p = 0$, $q > 2$, and $\theta = 0$, with

$$\Lambda_p = 0, \quad \Lambda_{pp} = 1 - \frac{4}{q^2} > 0;$$

- left branch: $p = \sqrt{2q} - q$, $0 < q < 2$, and $\theta = 0$, with

$$\Lambda_p = 0, \quad \Lambda_{pp} = 8 \left(\sqrt{\frac{2}{q}} - 1 \right) > 0.$$

On the two branches, except at their intersection, $\Lambda \equiv \Lambda(p)$ exhibits non-degenerate minima provided that q satisfies the restrictions mentioned above. This observation implies that, as we will see shortly, the bifurcation system (1.5) can be reduced to a couple of different second-order ODEs (one for each branch). At the critical point, however, $\Lambda \equiv \Lambda(p, q)$ attains a degenerate minimum characterised by a vanishing Hessian determinant – this arises because the 3D surface represented by the function remains flat for (p, q) satisfying $(p^2 + q)^4 = 4q^2$. As demonstrated in the next section, the asymptotic reduction of the full bifurcation system in this case results in a fourth-order ODE. These observations were confirmed in [1] using standard multiple-scale arguments. In the present work, we revisit that analysis with the help of the simplified framework introduced in CDC25, which serves to underscore some of the advantages offered by the alternative approach.

One could argue that our dismissal of ‘Case 2’ for the regime associated with the global minimum of the neutral stability curve was somewhat hasty. To some extent this is true; however, our approach has been guided by the numerical evidence presented in Figure 1. Taken at face value, one might consider allowing (p, q) to satisfy (2.7), even though such a choice would leave both p and q undetermined for the time being. We will return to this issue at the end of §5, where we will explain why this scenario is ultimately untenable.

To avoid introducing an excessive amount of new notation, some of the symbols used in the next section will be recycled. Since the three cases examined separately are mutually independent, this should not cause any confusion.

3 The critical case (global minimum)

It is convenient to re-scale the large parameter $\mu \gg 1$ to facilitate the various algebraic manipulations. To this end, we let $\varepsilon := \mu^{-1/6}$ and assume that $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$. As we expect the solutions to be localised at some point along the circumference of the cylinder, an interior-layer-type coordinate $Z = \mathcal{O}(1)$ is also introduced,

$$\theta = \theta_0 - \varepsilon^2 Z, \quad (-\infty < Z < +\infty), \quad (3.1)$$

where $\theta_0 \in [-\pi, \pi)$ remains to be determined.

The solutions of (1.5) will be sought with an ansatz of the form

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \varepsilon^4 + \lambda_2 \varepsilon^8 + \dots, \quad (3.2a)$$

$$q = q_0 + q_1 \varepsilon^2 + q_2 \varepsilon^4 + \dots, \quad (3.2b)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \widehat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) \exp(i\varepsilon^{-1}\Omega Z), \quad (3.2c)$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) = \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0(Z) + \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1(Z)\varepsilon^2 + \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_2(Z)\varepsilon^4 + \dots, \quad (3.2d)$$

in which $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_j(Z) := [\widehat{G}_j(Z), \widehat{H}_j(Z)]^T$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$). The quantities $\lambda_j, q_j, \Omega \in \mathbb{R}$, $\widehat{G}_j, \widehat{H}_j$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) will be determined as part of the solution, as explained below.

By employing the re-scaled variable and the specific form (3.2c) of the solution, the matrix differential operator \mathcal{L} in (1.5) can be expanded as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_1 + \varepsilon^4 \mathcal{L}_2 + \dots,$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{L}_j^{11} & \mathcal{L}_j^{12} \\ \mathcal{L}_j^{21} & \mathcal{L}_j^{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad (3.3)$$

and the components $\mathcal{L}_j^{\alpha\beta}$ ($\alpha, \beta \in \{1, 2\}$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) will be defined shortly. Substituting (3.2) into (1.5) leads to the usual sequence of order equations that follow from

$$(\mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_1 + \varepsilon^4 \mathcal{L}_2 + \dots)(\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \varepsilon^2 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_1 + \varepsilon^4 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_2 + \dots) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (3.4)$$

The first of these is obviously $\mathcal{L}_0 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \mathbf{0}$, in which

$$\mathcal{L}_0 := \begin{bmatrix} D^{11}(\Omega, q_0, \lambda_0, \theta_0) & D^{12}(q_0) \\ D^{21}(q_0) & D^{22}(\Omega, q_0) \end{bmatrix},$$

so we are essentially dealing with a homogeneous linear system of algebraic equations. A non-trivial solution $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 \neq \mathbf{0}$ can only exist if the determinant of the coefficient matrix vanishes. Expressed in terms of the dispersion function defined in (2.1), this condition translates into

$$\mathcal{D}(\Omega, q_0, \lambda_0, \theta_0) = 0. \quad (3.5)$$

Recalling the earlier analysis in §2, we find that

$$\Omega = 0, \quad q_0 = 2, \quad \lambda_0 = 1, \quad \theta_0 = 0, \quad (3.6)$$

and for future reference it is important to note that

$$\hat{H}_0(Z) = 2\hat{G}_0(Z). \quad (3.7)$$

The relevant components of the matrix operators in (3.3) required for the subsequent work in this section correspond to

$$\mathcal{L}_1^{11} := -\frac{1}{2} \mathring{D}_{pp}^{11} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2}, \quad \mathcal{L}_1^{12} := q_1, \quad \mathcal{L}_1^{21} := -4q_1, \quad \mathcal{L}_1^{22} := -\frac{1}{2} \mathring{D}_{pp}^{22} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2} + q_1 \mathring{D}_q^{22},$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_2^{11} &:= \frac{1}{24} \mathring{D}_{pppp}^{11} \frac{d^4}{dZ^4} - \frac{1}{2} q_1 \mathring{D}_{ppq}^{11} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2} + \left(\lambda_1 \mathring{D}_\lambda^{11} + \frac{1}{2} q_1^2 \mathring{D}_{qq}^{11} + \frac{1}{2} \mathring{D}_{\theta\theta}^{11} Z^2 \right), & \mathcal{L}_2^{12} &:= q_2, \\ \mathcal{L}_2^{21} &:= -4q_2, & \mathcal{L}_2^{22} &:= \frac{1}{24} \mathring{D}_{pppp}^{22} \frac{d^4}{dZ^4} - \frac{1}{2} q_1 \mathring{D}_{ppq}^{22} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2} + \left(\frac{1}{2} q_1^2 \mathring{D}_{qq}^{22} + q_2 \mathring{D}_q^{22} \right); \end{aligned}$$

here, the small circle above the D -quantities indicates evaluation at $(p, q, \lambda, \theta) = (\Omega, q_0, \lambda_0, \theta_0)$, as defined in (3.6). The coefficients of these differential operators are very simple and are listed below for the sake of completeness

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{D}_{pppp}^{11} = \mathring{D}_{pppp}^{22} &= 24, & \mathring{D}_{pp}^{11} = \mathring{D}_{pp}^{22} &= 8, & \mathring{D}_\lambda^{11} &= -8, \\ \mathring{D}_{ppq}^{11} = \mathring{D}_{ppq}^{22} &= 4, & \mathring{D}_{qq}^{11} = \mathring{D}_{qq}^{22} &= 2, & \mathring{D}_{\theta\theta}^{11} &= 8, & \mathring{D}_q^{22} &= 4. \end{aligned}$$

The next-order equation corresponds to an inhomogeneous linear system $\mathcal{L}_0 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_1 = -\mathcal{L}_1 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0$, whose solvability[†] demands that

$$-4\hat{G}_1(Z) + 2\hat{H}_1(Z) = 4\frac{d^2 \hat{G}_0}{dZ^2} - q_1 \hat{H}_0(Z). \quad (3.8)$$

[†]This condition amounts to multiplying the first equation of the linear system by 2 and then subtracting it from the second equation

The third order equation turns out to be of the form $\mathcal{L}_0 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_2 = -\mathcal{L}_1 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1 - \mathcal{L}_2 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0$; applying one more time the same solvability condition as above, in conjunction with (3.7) and (3.8), eventually gives the fourth-order differential equation

$$\frac{d^4 \widehat{G}_0}{dZ^4} - q_1 \frac{d^2 \widehat{G}_0}{dZ^2} + \left(\frac{q_1^2 - 8\lambda_1}{4} + Z^2 \right) \widehat{G}_0 = 0, \quad (3.9)$$

which agrees with the earlier result from [1] (see equation (4.11) therein).

4 The right branch

For the new situation it is advantageous to define $\varepsilon := \mu^{-1/4}$ and assume that $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$. As in the previous case, an interior-layer-type coordinate $Z = \mathcal{O}(1)$ is also introduced,

$$\theta = \theta_0 - \varepsilon Z, \quad (-\infty < Z < +\infty), \quad (4.1)$$

with $\theta_0 \in [-\pi, \pi)$ to be found.

This time we are not interested to constrain $q > 2$, so we will treat it as a free $\mathcal{O}(1)$ parameter. The solutions of (1.5) will be sought with

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \varepsilon^2 + \lambda_2 \varepsilon^4 + \dots, \quad (4.2a)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \widehat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) \exp(i\varepsilon^{-1} \Omega Z), \quad (4.2b)$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) = \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0(Z) + \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1(Z) \varepsilon^2 + \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_2(Z) \varepsilon^4 + \dots, \quad (4.2c)$$

where $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_j(Z) := [\widehat{G}_j(Z), \widehat{H}_j(Z)]^T$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$). The quantities $\lambda_j, \Omega \in \mathbb{R}, \widehat{G}_j, \widehat{H}_j$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) will be determined as outlined below.

By employing the re-scaled variable and the specific form (4.2b) of the solution, the matrix differential operator \mathcal{L} in (1.5) can be expanded as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_1 + \dots,$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{L}_j^{11} & \mathcal{L}_j^{12} \\ \mathcal{L}_j^{21} & \mathcal{L}_j^{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (4.3)$$

and the components \mathcal{L}_j will be defined shortly. Substituting (4.2) into (1.5) leads to the usual sequence of order equations that follow by expanding the product

$$(\mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_1 + \dots) (\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \varepsilon^2 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1 + \dots) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (4.4)$$

At leading-order, $\mathcal{L}_0 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \mathbf{0}$, where

$$\mathcal{L}_0 := \begin{bmatrix} D^{11}(\Omega, q, \lambda_0, \theta_0) & D^{12}(q) \\ D^{21}(q) & D^{22}(\Omega, q) \end{bmatrix}.$$

A non-trivial solution $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 \neq \mathbf{0}$ of this homogeneous linear system can only exist if the determinant of the coefficient matrix vanishes. In terms of the dispersion function,

$$\mathcal{D}(\Omega, q, \lambda_0, \theta_0) = 0, \quad (4.5)$$

and the results from §2 indicate that

$$\Omega = 0, \quad q > 2, \quad \lambda_0 = \frac{1}{4} \left(q + \frac{4}{q} \right), \quad \theta_0 = 0; \quad (4.6)$$

we also note for future reference that

$$q\hat{H}_0(Z) = 4\hat{G}_0(Z). \quad (4.7)$$

The relevant components of the matrix operators in (4.3) are

$$\mathcal{L}_1^{11} := -\frac{1}{2}\mathring{D}_{pp}^{11} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2} + \left(\lambda_1 \mathring{D}_\lambda^{11} + \frac{1}{2}\mathring{D}_{\theta\theta}^{11} Z^2 \right), \quad \mathcal{L}_1^{22} := -\frac{1}{2}\mathring{D}_{pp}^{22} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2}, \quad \mathcal{L}_1^{12} \equiv \mathcal{L}_1^{21} := 0.$$

The small circle above the D -quantities has a similar connotation as before, i.e. it indicates evaluation at $(p, q, \lambda, \theta) = (\Omega, q, \lambda_0, \theta_0)$, as defined in (4.6). For the sake of completeness the coefficients of these differential operators are included below

$$\mathring{D}_{pp}^{11} = \mathring{D}_{pp}^{22} = 4q, \quad \mathring{D}_{\theta\theta}^{11} = q^2 + 4, \quad \mathring{D}_\lambda^{11} = -4q.$$

At first-order, the product (4.4) gives an inhomogeneous linear system $\mathcal{L}_0 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_1 = -\mathcal{L}_1 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0$. The solvability condition requires multiplying the first equation by q and subtracting it from the second equation. Making further use of (4.7) produces a Weber-Hermite type equation

$$\frac{d^2 \hat{G}_0}{dZ^2} + \left\{ \left(\frac{2q^2 \lambda_1}{q^2 - 4} \right) - \left[\frac{q(q^2 + 4)}{q^2 - 4} \right] Z^2 \right\} \hat{G}_0 = 0. \quad (4.8)$$

The result obtained is equivalent to equation (5.6) in [1], where additional remarks can be found.

5 The left branch

This last scenario is very similar to the one discussed in §4, the major difference being the presence of a fast spatial oscillation in the eigenmodes. The small parameter is still $\varepsilon := \mu^{-1/4}$ and the definition of the interior-layer coordinate $Z = \mathcal{O}(1)$ remains the same,

$$\theta = \theta_0 - \varepsilon Z, \quad (-\infty < Z < +\infty), \quad (5.1)$$

with $\theta_0 \in [-\pi, \pi)$ to be found.

In light of the discussion in §2 it will be assumed that $q = \mathcal{O}(1)$ with $0 < q < 2$. To approximate the solutions of (1.5) we set

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \varepsilon^2 + \lambda_2 \varepsilon^4 + \dots, \quad (5.2a)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \hat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) \exp(i\varepsilon^{-1} \Omega Z), \quad (5.2b)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) = \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0(Z) + \hat{\mathbf{u}}_1(Z) \varepsilon + \hat{\mathbf{u}}_2(Z) \varepsilon^2 + \dots, \quad (5.2c)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_j(Z) := [\hat{G}_j(Z), \hat{H}_j(Z)]^T$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$). The quantities λ_j , $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}$, \hat{G}_j , \hat{H}_j ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) are found by pursuing the same strategy as in the previously discussed cases.

The use of (5.2b) suggests that the matrix differential operator \mathcal{L} in (1.5) can be expanded as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon \mathcal{L}_1 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_2 + \dots,$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_j = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{L}_j^{11} & \mathcal{L}_j^{12} \\ \mathcal{L}_j^{21} & \mathcal{L}_j^{22} \end{bmatrix}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, \quad (5.3)$$

and the expressions of the components of \mathcal{L}_j will follow shortly. Substituting (5.2) into (1.5) leads to

$$(\mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon \mathcal{L}_1 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_2 + \dots) (\hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \varepsilon \hat{\mathbf{u}}_1 + \varepsilon^2 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_2 + \dots) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (5.4)$$

The leading-order equation remains $\mathcal{L}_0 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \mathbf{0}$, where

$$\mathcal{L}_0 := \begin{bmatrix} D^{11}(\Omega, q, \lambda_0, \theta_0) & D^{12}(q) \\ D^{21}(q) & D^{22}(\Omega, q) \end{bmatrix};$$

to ensure a non-trivial solution, the determinant of this matrix must vanish. By invoking the dispersion function (2.1), we impose the condition $\mathcal{D}(\Omega, q, \lambda_0, \theta_0) = 0$, which fixes the leading-order unknowns in (5.2) (see §2)

$$\Omega = \sqrt{\sqrt{2q} - q}, \quad 0 < q < 2, \quad \lambda_0 = 1, \quad \theta_0 = 0. \quad (5.5)$$

Another useful bit of information derived from the solution of the leading-order problem is

$$\hat{H}_0(Z) = 2\hat{G}_0(Z). \quad (5.6)$$

The relevant components of the matrix operators in (4.3) needed to complete the work in this section are recorded below

$$\mathcal{L}_1^{11} := -i\mathring{D}_p^{11} \frac{d}{dZ}, \quad \mathcal{L}_1^{22} := -i\mathring{D}_p^{22} \frac{d}{dZ}, \quad \mathcal{L}_1^{12} \equiv \mathcal{L}_1^{21} := 0.$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}_2^{11} := -\frac{1}{2}\mathring{D}_{pp}^{11} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2} + \left(\lambda_1 \mathring{D}_\lambda^{11} + \frac{1}{2}\mathring{D}_{\theta\theta}^{11} Z^2 \right), \quad \mathcal{L}_2^{22} := -\frac{1}{2}\mathring{D}_{pp}^{22} \frac{d^2}{dZ^2}, \quad \mathcal{L}_2^{12} \equiv \mathcal{L}_2^{21} := 0.$$

The small circle above the D -quantities indicates evaluation at $(p, q, \lambda, \theta) = (\Omega, q, \lambda_0, \theta_0)$, as defined in (5.5). For the sake of completeness the coefficients of these differential operators are included below

$$\begin{aligned} \mathring{D}_p^{11} = \mathring{D}_p^{22} &= 4\Omega\sqrt{2q}, & \mathring{D}_{pp}^{11} = \mathring{D}_{pp}^{22} &= 4(3\Omega^2 + q), \\ \mathring{D}_\lambda^{11} &= -4q, & \mathring{D}_{\theta\theta}^{11} &= 4q. \end{aligned}$$

At first-order, the product (5.4) gives an inhomogeneous linear system $\mathcal{L}_0 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_1 = -\mathcal{L}_1 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0$. The solvability condition is automatically satisfied because of (5.6). The actual solution of this algebraic system shows that $\hat{G}_1 \equiv \hat{G}_1(Z)$ is arbitrary at this stage, but $\hat{H}_1 \equiv \hat{H}_1(Z)$ obeys

$$\hat{H}_1(Z) = 2\hat{G}_1(Z) + 4i\sqrt{2}(\Omega/\sqrt{q}) \frac{d\hat{G}_0}{dZ}. \quad (5.7)$$

The solution $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0$ is fixed at the next-order by another routine application of the solvability condition for the linear system $\mathcal{L}_0\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_2 = -\mathcal{L}_1\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1 - \mathcal{L}_2\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0$. Taking into account (5.6) and (5.7) the final outcome is once again a re-scaled Weber-Hermite equation

$$8\Omega^2 \frac{d^2 \widehat{G}_0}{dZ^2} + q(2\lambda_1 - Z^2) \widehat{G}_0 = 0, \quad (5.8)$$

which was also recovered with the standard multiple-scale asymptotic method in [1]; see equation (6.6) in that reference.

To conclude this section, we revisit the issue of the unsuitability of (2.7) in the critical case. While this condition is mathematically valid, it contradicts the minimum property of the eigenvalue in the bifurcation system (1.5). To illustrate this, we use (5.8) to obtain $\lambda_1 = \Omega\sqrt{2/q}$ (see §6 in [1]), allowing us to express the eigenvalue as

$$\lambda = 1 + \left(\frac{2}{\sqrt{q}} - \sqrt{2} \right) \mu^{-1/2} + \mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1}). \quad (5.9)$$

Given that $\lambda \equiv \lambda(q)$, minimising (5.9) over $q \in (0, 2]$ yields $q = 2$, which in turn implies $\Omega = 0$. Consequently, (5.8) loses its relevance, naturally leading us back to the asymptotic regime already covered in §3.

6 Remarks

The example revisited here brings out several complementary aspects to the analysis presented in CDC25. First, the dispersion relation considered in this study originates from a classical model for the buckling of cylindrical shells under pure bending. While this setup involves a somewhat simpler structure at the critical points than that used in CDC25, it is more representative of standard two-dimensional buckling models. Second, the example offers further evidence for our earlier claim that the order of the reduced equation reflects the degree of degeneracy exhibited by the dispersion relation. This is clearly demonstrated by the fact that, depending on the nature of the stationary points, the reduced problem may take the form of either a second- or a fourth-order ordinary differential equation. In general, explicit analytical results are more easily obtained in the former case. Additional insights can be found in [1], which readers may find helpful for comparison.

For more complex problems, linear pre-buckling deformations may be less tractable than those encountered here, potentially leading to a dispersion relation that does not lend itself to closed-form analysis. In such cases, numerical methods can be employed to locate stationary points, as demonstrated in [4]. Once the necessary coefficients of the operators \mathcal{L}_j (e.g. see (4.4)) are determined through this analysis, the subsequent steps remain unchanged.

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Degenerate asymptotic phenomena in the buckling of inhomogeneously pre-stressed cylindrical shells

(Supplementary online material II)

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1 Introduction

This note represents the second part of the supplementary online material accompanying the main paper (hereafter referred to as CDC25*). The configuration explored here is a variation of the pure-bending scenario in the first part, but with a slight “twist”: the cylindrical shell is taken to be internally pressurised. While this modification may appear minor, it introduces a significant change to the reduced model, as will be demonstrated in the following sections.

The general scenario we explore is a classical one in engineering applications and has been investigated in earlier studies, notably by Weingarten [1] and Reddy & Calladine [2], among others. Weingarten’s work was purely numerical, whereas Reddy & Calladine employed a series of ad-hoc mathematical arguments to derive approximate expressions for key quantities such as the critical bending moment and axial buckling wavelength. Although some of their derivations contain mathematical inaccuracies, the resulting approximations are remarkably robust. A secondary aim of this note is to demonstrate how straightforward asymptotic methods can be used to derive these results more systematically, avoiding such inconsistencies.

The configuration of interest is very similar to that considered in Part I (also, see [4, 5]). We examine a closed thin elastic cylindrical shell of length L , radius R , and thickness h , subjected to pure bending. The applied loads at both ends are statically equivalent to a moment M acting in the plane of curvature of the shell. In addition, the cylinder is also internally pressurised, with the internal pressure denoted by $P > 0$. The analyses in the aforementioned studies [1, 2] are based on the Donnell-Mushtari-Vlasov (DMV) shallow-shell buckling equations, formulated in terms of the transverse displacement $w \equiv w(x, \theta)$ and a stress function $F \equiv F(x, \theta)$. Denoting the pre-buckling membrane stress resultants by \dot{N}_{xx} , $\dot{N}_{x\theta}$, and $\dot{N}_{\theta\theta}$, the buckling equations can be written as

$$\begin{cases} D\nabla^4 w - \left(\dot{N}_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + 2\dot{N}_{x\theta} \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial \theta} + \dot{N}_{\theta\theta} \frac{1}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} \right) - \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right) = 0, \\ \nabla^4 F + \frac{Eh}{R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

where $D \equiv Eh^3/12(1 - \nu^2)$ represents the bending rigidity, the Laplacian is defined according to $\nabla^2 := \partial_x^2 + R^{-2}\partial_\theta^2$, and $\nabla^4 := \nabla^2 \nabla^2$. The pre-buckling stress distribution corresponds to the membrane

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solution for a cylindrical shell subjected to the combined action of internal (hydrostatic) pressure and in-plane bending moments, as in the problem discussed in Part I (see [4, 5]). As is well known, by the superposition of the two loading mechanisms mentioned,

$$\dot{N}_{xx} = \frac{1}{2}PR - \frac{M}{\pi R^2} \cos \theta, \quad \dot{N}_{\theta\theta} = PR, \quad \dot{N}_{x\theta} \equiv 0, \quad (1.2)$$

and it is clear that when $P = 0$ the above basic state reduces to that of the pure bending problem previously discussed. Here we are interested in the case $P \neq 0$; further restrictions on this parameter will be specified shortly.

On substituting (1.2) into (1.1), the resulting equations turn out to be amenable to solutions with separable variables of the form

$$[w, F]^T = [G(\theta), H(\theta)]^T \sin\left(\frac{q_m x}{R}\right), \quad q_m := \frac{m\pi R}{L}, \quad (m = 1, 2, \dots), \quad (1.3)$$

where the superscript T stands for ‘transposition’; q_m represents the *axial* buckle half-wavelength, while the azimuthal amplitudes $G \equiv G(\theta)$, $H \equiv H(\theta)$ denote the new main dependent variables. Use of (1.3) in (1.1) shows that these new functions satisfy a set of two coupled fourth-order ordinary differential equations, which can be simplified further by introducing the following non-dimensional quantities

$$\bar{G} := \frac{G}{R}, \quad \bar{H} := \sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)} \frac{H}{ERh^2}, \quad \mu := \sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)} \frac{R}{h} \gg 1, \quad q := \mu^{-1} q_m^2, \quad (1.4a)$$

$$N_* := \frac{Eh}{\sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)}} \left(\frac{h}{R}\right), \quad \lambda := \frac{N_b}{N_*} \quad (N_b := M/(\pi R^2)), \quad \Pi := \frac{\mu^2}{\sqrt{3(1-\nu^2)}} \left(\frac{P}{E}\right). \quad (1.4b)$$

The normalisation term N_* represents the theoretical *compressive buckling stress resultant* for an infinitely long elastic cylindrical shell; N_b is a dimensional quantity representing the “extreme fibre bending stress resultant” [2]. It is important to note that the non-dimensional pressure defined in (1.4b) is a secondary, prescribed parameter and may span various orders of magnitude. In this work, following [1, 2], we assume $\Pi = \mathcal{O}(1)$.

Removing the bars from the re-scaled variables, the reduced bifurcation equations can then be cast in the more compact form

$$\mathcal{L} \left(i\mu^{-1/2} \frac{d}{d\theta}, q, \lambda, \theta \right) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u} \equiv \mathbf{u}(\theta) := [G(\theta), H(\theta)]^T, \quad (1.5)$$

where

$$\mathcal{L} \equiv \mathcal{L}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) := \begin{bmatrix} D^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) & D^{12}(q) \\ D^{21}(q) & D^{22}(p, q) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.6)$$

and

$$D^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) := p^4 + 2(q + 2\Pi)p^2 + q[q + 2(\Pi - 2\lambda \cos \theta)], \quad D^{12}(q) := 4q, \quad (1.7a)$$

$$D^{21}(q) := -q, \quad D^{22}(p, q) := (p^2 + q)^2. \quad (1.7b)$$

As in the scenario discussed in Part I, the primary objective here is to explore asymptotic simplifications of (1.5) that enable accurate approximations of the critical values of λ . Although the

governing equations are relatively straightforward, the task is nontrivial due to the dependence of the eigen-parameter on the artificially introduced quantity q (or, equivalently, q_m), as defined in (1.3) and (1.4a). Since $\lambda \equiv \lambda(q)$, from a practical point of view the interest lies in determining its minimum values – which, in general, must be obtained numerically.

Figure 1: Samples of *neutral stability curves* for the bifurcation system (1.5) corresponding to $R/h = 4.5 \times 10^2$, $\nu = 0.3$, and three different values of the (non-dimensional) internal pressure Π ; see (1.4a) for the definition of the asymptotic parameter μ . The absolute minima of the function $\lambda = \lambda(q)$ correspond to $q \simeq 2$.

Figure 1 presents several typical numerical examples illustrating the behaviour of $q \mapsto \lambda(q)$ for $\mu \simeq 743$; the global minima of these curves identify the critical values of λ and q (or, equivalently, q_m). In the interest of brevity, we do not include additional examples of eigenmodes along the neutral stability curve. The situation is broadly similar to the detailed numerical study in [4]: on the left branch (i.e., for $q \lesssim 2$) the eigenmodes are modulated by a Gaussian envelope and exhibit rapid spatial oscillations. By contrast, on the right branch (i.e., $q \gtrsim 2$), these oscillations are absent, although the localised envelope shape is still preserved. The key difference arises at the global minimum of the curves shown in Figure 1.

In the next section, we analyse the dispersion function associated with the system (1.5) to provide a rational explanation for the discrepancies between the pure bending problems *with* and *without* internal pressure. Somewhat unexpectedly, these differences are linked to the degeneracy of the dispersion function, or the absence thereof.

2 The dispersion function

The asymptotic structure of (1.5) in the limit $\mu \gg 1$ depends on a suitably defined *dispersion function*, which in our case is given by the determinant of (1.6). By setting to zero the corresponding expression allows us to express λ as a function of the other parameters (p , q , and θ); in particular, we find $\lambda = \Lambda(p, q, \theta)$ with

$$\Lambda(p, q, \theta) := \frac{1}{4q \cos \theta} \left[(p^2 + q)^2 + \frac{4q^2}{(p^2 + q)^2} + 2\Pi(2p^2 + q) \right]. \quad (2.1)$$

Our immediate goal is to identify the minimum of the function defined in (2.1), subject to the following restrictions

$$p \geq 0, \quad q > 0, \quad -\pi \leq \theta < \pi. \quad (2.2)$$

The stationary points of Λ can be found by solving $\Lambda_p = \Lambda_q = \Lambda_\theta = 0$, where the subscripts are used to indicate partial differentiation with respect to the corresponding variable (a convention that will be employed henceforth). Note that the third equation is decoupled from the other two; its possible solutions include $\theta = \theta_* := -\pi$ and $\theta = \theta_* := 0$, with the former being inadmissible as it violates the initial assumption $\Lambda > 0$. As for the remaining two equations, they can be reduced to

$$\Lambda_p = 0 \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \left(\frac{p}{q} \right) \left[(p^2 + q) - \frac{4q^2}{(p^2 + q)^3} + 2\Pi \right] = 0, \quad (2.3a)$$

$$\Lambda_q = 0 \quad \Longrightarrow \quad \frac{(q - p^2)}{4q^2} \left[(p^2 + q) - \frac{4q^2}{(p^2 + q)^3} \right] - \Pi \left(\frac{p}{q} \right)^2 = 0. \quad (2.3b)$$

Using the first of these equations, we find that two cases must be considered. If $p = 0$ then equation (2.3a) is satisfied, while equation (2.3b) yields $q^2(q^2 - 4) = 0$, implying $q = 2$. The other alternative is that the second factor in the product from equation (2.3a) vanishes. Substituting this into the second equation leads to $p^2 + q = 0$, which cannot yield any admissible solutions, as the dispersion function is only defined for $p^2 + q \neq 0$. It follows that the unique critical point of Λ consistent with the constraints (2.2) is given by $p = p_* := 0$ and $q = q_* := 2$. We also have

$$\Lambda_{pp}^0 = \Pi \geq 0, \quad \Lambda_{pq}^0 = 0, \quad \Lambda_{qq}^0 = \frac{1}{4}, \quad \Lambda_{ppp}^0 = 0, \quad \Lambda_{pppp}^0 = 12. \quad (2.4)$$

where the ‘zero’ superscript indicates that the corresponding partial derivatives are evaluated at the critical point (p_*, q_*, θ_*) found above, which is evidently a minimum. In light of (2.4), it becomes clear that the case $\Pi \neq 0$ differs fundamentally from the unpressurised case $\Pi = 0$ (previously examined in [4] and briefly re-visited in Part I of this supplement). Whereas the reduced equation for the pure bending problem without internal pressure was fourth-order, we now anticipate that the system (1.5) admits an asymptotic simplification to a *second-order* differential equation. This expectation will be confirmed in the following section.

3 The global minimum of the response curve $\lambda = \lambda(q)$

The strategy that we follow mirrors closely the calculations in CDC25. We start by introducing the new asymptotic parameter $\varepsilon := \mu^{-1/4}$, and assume that $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1$. As the solutions are expected to

be localised at some point along the circumference of the cylinder (e.g., see [1]), an interior-layer-type coordinate $Z = \mathcal{O}(1)$ is also introduced,

$$\theta = \theta_0 - \varepsilon Z, \quad (-\infty < Z < +\infty), \quad (3.1)$$

where $\theta_0 \in [-\pi, \pi)$ remains to be determined.

The solutions of (1.5) will be sought with an ansatz of the form

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 \varepsilon + \lambda_2 \varepsilon^2 + \dots, \quad (3.2a)$$

$$q = q_0 + q_1 \varepsilon^4 + \dots, \quad (3.2b)$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \widehat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) \exp(i\varepsilon^{-1} \Omega Z), \quad (3.2c)$$

$$\widehat{\mathbf{u}}(Z) = \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0(Z) + \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1(Z) \varepsilon + \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_2(Z) \varepsilon^2 + \dots, \quad (3.2d)$$

in which $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_j(Z) := [\widehat{G}_j(Z), \widehat{H}_j(Z)]^T$ ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$). The quantities λ_j , q_j , $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}$, \widehat{G}_j , \widehat{H}_j ($j = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) will be determined as part of the solution, as explained below.

By employing the re-scaled variable and the specific form (3.2c) of the solution, the matrix differential operator \mathcal{L} in (1.5) can be expanded as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon \mathcal{L}_1 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_2 + \dots,$$

where

$$\mathcal{L}_0 := \mathcal{L}(\Omega, q_0, \lambda_0, \theta_0), \quad \mathcal{L}_1 := \lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_\lambda^0, \quad \mathcal{L}_2 := -\frac{1}{2} \mathcal{L}_{pp}^0 \frac{d^2}{dY^2} + \left(\frac{1}{2} Y^2 \mathcal{L}_{\theta\theta}^0 + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_\lambda^0 \right). \quad (3.3)$$

Substituting (3.2) into (1.5) leads to the usual sequence of order equations that follow from

$$(\mathcal{L}_0 + \varepsilon \mathcal{L}_1 + \varepsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_2 + \dots) (\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \varepsilon \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1 + \varepsilon^2 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_2 + \dots) = \mathbf{0}. \quad (3.4)$$

The first of these is obviously $\mathcal{L}_0 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 = \mathbf{0}$, in which

$$\mathcal{L}_0 := \begin{bmatrix} D^{11}(\Omega, q_0, \lambda_0, \theta_0) & D^{12}(q_0) \\ D^{21}(q_0) & D^{22}(\Omega, q_0) \end{bmatrix}.$$

A non-trivial solution $\widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0 \neq \mathbf{0}$ can only exist if the determinant of the coefficient matrix vanishes. This leads to the dispersion relation, which in turn yields $\lambda_0 = \Lambda(\Omega, q_0, \theta_0)$. By minimising this function we obtain $(\Omega, q_0, \theta_0) = (p_*, q_*, \theta_*)$, the values identified in §2; also, we note that

$$\lambda_0 = \Lambda(p_*, q_*, \theta_*) = \frac{\Pi + 2}{2} > 1. \quad (3.5)$$

Another key piece of information that transpires from the zeroth-order system is that

$$\widehat{G}_0(Z) = 2\widehat{H}_0(Z).$$

The first-order equation corresponds to an inhomogeneous linear system $\mathcal{L}_0 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_1 = -\mathcal{L}_1 \widehat{\mathbf{u}}_0$, whose solvability trivially requires $\lambda_1 = 0$, so $\mathcal{L}_1 \equiv \mathbf{0}$; we also find that $G_1(Z) = 2H_1(Z)$. It is at the

next order that we identify λ_2 . Indeed, the solvability condition for the inhomogeneous linear system $\mathcal{L}_0 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_2 = -\mathcal{L}_2 \hat{\mathbf{u}}_0$ leads to the parabolic-cylinder equation

$$\Pi \frac{d^2 \hat{G}_0}{dZ^2} + (2\lambda_2 - \lambda_0 Z^2) \hat{G}_0 = 0, \quad (3.6)$$

whence

$$\lambda_2 = \left(k + \frac{1}{2} \right) \sqrt{2\lambda_0(\lambda_0 - 1)}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad (3.7)$$

and the value of interest in our context is obtained for $k = 0$. Recall that equation (3.6) was derived under the assumption $\Pi = \mathcal{O}(1)$; consequently, the same assumption underlies formula (3.7), which follows directly from it.

To summarise, we have obtained the following asymptotic approximation for the (non-dimensional) critical load of the internally pressurised cylinder subject to a pure bending moment,

$$\lambda = \left(\frac{\Pi + 2}{2} \right) \left[1 + \mu^{-1/2} \sqrt{\frac{\Pi}{2(\Pi + 2)}} + \mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1}) \right], \quad \text{for } \mu \gg 1. \quad (3.8)$$

Higher-order calculations do not pose any particular difficulties, as the next-order equations admit particular solutions that can be determined in closed form. Given the close similarity to the analysis presented in §6 of [4], we do not pursue these calculations here and instead refer interested readers to the aforementioned reference.

The result we got for λ_2 matches the structural form of its counterpart in reference [2] (see Table 1 on page 648). The only difference lies in the fact that those authors adopted a fixed Poisson's ratio, $\nu = 0.3$, so their final expressions include an explicit numerical coefficient. Nonetheless, the two results are fully consistent. In our case, the pre-factor in the expression for $\mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1/2})$ -term can be recovered by isolating the ratio (h/R) in the definition of μ , which yields $(1/2) \cdot [3(1 - \nu^2)]^{-1/4}$; for $\nu = 0.3$ this evaluates to approximately $0.3890 \simeq 0.39$, matching the value reported in [2]. Comparisons between an equivalent form of formula (3.8) and direct numerical simulations of the bifurcation system (1.5) can be found in [2], specifically in Figures 5 and 6.

4 The Morley-Batdorf bifurcation equation

The numerical study conducted by Weingarten [1] was not based on the standard DMV shallow-shell theory, but rather on a modified formulation incorporating the refinements proposed by Morley [6] together with a simplified approach introduced by Batdorf [7]. These ‘‘improvements’’ can be consolidated into a single equation for the transverse displacement w , the stress function F being eliminated entirely. It is worth noting that Morley's modification effectively replaces the bi-Laplacian ∇^4 in the first equation of the system (1.1) with the operator $(\nabla^2 + R^{-2})^2$. In our notation, the buckling equation employed by Weingarten can be written as

$$D \left(\nabla^2 + \frac{1}{R^2} \right)^2 w - \left(\dot{N}_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + 2\dot{N}_{x\theta} \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial \theta} + \dot{N}_{\theta\theta} \frac{1}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} \right) + \frac{Eh}{R^2} \nabla^{-4} \left(\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} \right) = 0, \quad (4.1)$$

where the inverse of the bi-Laplacian, ∇^{-4} , is formally defined by the relation $\nabla^{-4}(\nabla^4 f) = f$ for any sufficiently smooth function $f \equiv f(x, \theta)$.

Since Morley's so-called improved theory is derived in a fairly ad-hoc manner – and itself not free from mathematical inconsistencies (e.g., see [8]) – it is unclear whether the use of equation (4.1) is

better suited to the present buckling scenario. One particular concern is whether employing (4.1) might give rise to a different asymptotic structure for an internally pressurised thin cylinder subjected to pure bending. With regard to this second aspect, it will be shown here that this is not the case: the two-term result (3.8) derived in the previous section remains unchanged. Nonetheless, the use of (4.1) does affect the higher-order correction terms in that asymptotic expansion, typically at order $\mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1})$ and beyond.

In keeping with the formulation adopted in Part I and the earlier sections of this note, we do not work directly with equation (4.1); instead, we employ an equivalent system given by,

$$\begin{cases} D \left(\nabla^2 + \frac{1}{R^2} \right)^2 w - \left(\dot{N}_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + 2\dot{N}_{x\theta} \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial \theta} + \dot{N}_{\theta\theta} \frac{1}{R^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} \right) - \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 F}{\partial x^2} \right) = 0, \\ \nabla^4 F + \frac{Eh}{R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

Equation (4.1) follows directly from (4.2). To derive it, we take the second partial derivative with respect to ‘ x ’ of the second equation in the above system, observing that this derivative commutes with the bi-harmonic operator ∇^4 ; therefore, their order can be interchanged in the corresponding term of the transformed equation. Further application of the properties of the inverse operator ∇^{-4} yields an explicit representation of $\partial^2 F / \partial x^2$ in terms of w . This expression is then substituted back into the first equation of (4.2) to obtain the desired result.

Using the non-dimensional variables introduced in (1.4), the new system (4.2) can be cast in a form similar to (1.5), namely,

$$\mathcal{L}_{\#} \left(i\mu^{-1/2} \frac{d}{d\theta}, q, \lambda, \theta, \mu^{-1} \right) \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{u} \equiv \mathbf{u}(\theta) := [G(\theta), H(\theta)]^T, \quad (4.3)$$

where the original \mathcal{L} has been replaced by the modified expression

$$\mathcal{L}_{\#} \equiv \mathcal{L}_{\#}(p, q, \lambda, \theta, \mu^{-1}) := \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{D}^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) & D^{12}(q) \\ D^{21}(q) & D^{22}(p, q) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4.4)$$

The matrix entries are as defined in (1.7), except for \tilde{D}^{11} , which now includes dependence on $\mu^{-1} \ll 1$ and corresponds to

$$\tilde{D}^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) := D^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta) + \mu^{-1} D_a^{11}(p, q) + \mu^{-2} D_b^{11}, \quad (4.5)$$

with

$$D_a^{11}(p, q) := -2(p^2 + q) \quad \text{and} \quad D_b^{11} := 1; \quad (4.6)$$

the definition of $D^{11}(p, q, \lambda, \theta)$ remains unchanged from that given previously in (1.7).

In view of the specific structure of the modified bifurcation system in (4.3), it is clear that the additional terms in the definition of \tilde{D}^{11} will not affect the two-term formula recorded in (3.8). For the sake of completeness, we include in Table 1 a set of comparisons between the critical load predictions obtained numerically from (1.5) and (4.3), respectively. For the chosen values of the Poisson’s ratio (ν) and the aspect ratio R/h , we get $\mu \simeq 743$. A quick inspection of the critical loads listed in the table indicates that the differences between the corresponding values for a given pressure Π is roughly $\mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1})$, which confirms our earlier claims.

Table 1: Sample of critical loads obtained via direct numerical integration of equations (1.5) and (4.3), denoted by λ_D and λ_{MB} , respectively. The results correspond to $\nu = 0.3$, $R/h = 4.5 \times 10^2$, with the non-dimensional internal pressure listed in the first column of the table.

Pressure (Π)	λ_{MB}	λ_D
1.6	1.831165	1.831863
1.8	1.933961	1.934646
2.0	2.036721	2.037406
2.2	2.139462	2.140147
2.4	2.242188	2.242872
2.6	2.344901	2.345586
2.8	2.447644	2.448288
3.0	2.550297	2.550982

Some remarks are in order regarding the values presented in Table 1. Both sets of bifurcation equations were formulated using the modal parameter q_m rather than its rescaled version q , and the corresponding minima of the curves $\lambda \equiv \lambda(q_m)$ were sought by incrementing q_m in steps of size 0.5. With this caveat in mind, it is expected that marginally different results may be obtained by refining the step size; however, such differences are typically small and do not affect the overall conclusions. For further discussion of similar numerical considerations, the reader is referred to the supplementary online material in our recent study [9].

Determining whether the Morley-Batdorf bifurcation equation provides a more realistic description of the buckling scenarios considered here would require direct comparison with numerical solutions of the full three-dimensional elasticity equations, an analysis that lies beyond the scope of this brief study. We note in passing that the predictions λ_{MB} in Table 1 are consistently slightly less than their λ_D counterparts.

5 Discussion and final remarks

As is both intuitively clear and well-established (e.g., [10, 11]), internal pressure within a thin cylindrical shell has a stabilising effect with respect to its resistance to pure bending moments. This stabilising influence manifests in several ways throughout the mathematical developments of both the present study and our earlier work [4]. First, the leading-order critical load for the pressurised cylinder is always greater than unity, in contrast to the unpressurised case discussed in [4] and Part I of this supplement. As noted in [2], the two-term asymptotic approximation derived here does not reduce to that of the unpressurised case, due to the fact that the expansions for the critical eigenvalue λ involve different powers of the large parameter $\mu \gg 1$, even though the definition of μ remains unchanged in both cases. Furthermore, when $\Pi = 0$, equation (3.6) becomes irrelevant, since Π appears as a multiplicative factor in the highest-order derivative term. This observation is further supported by the analysis in §2 – see in particular equation (2.4) – which shows that the minimum point $(p_*, q_*, \theta_*) = (0, 2, 0)$ becomes degenerate in the absence of internal pressure. This degeneracy explains why the reduced critical problem in [4] is governed by a fourth-order differential equation.

An alternative way to contrast the reduced models in the two cases is to observe that, for the

unpressurised cylinder, the asymptotic reduction yields an ODE containing both fourth- and second-order derivatives (see §3 in Part I). This indicates that bending and membrane effects contribute comparably to the instability mechanism. In contrast, for the internally pressurised case, membrane effects dominate, as expected, and this is reflected in a reduced model governed by a second-order differential equation. In both formulations, the non-differentiated terms resemble those of a Winkler-foundation model, where the elastic stiffness is position-dependent – a feature that arises naturally from the curved geometry of the shell and the particular non-symmetric loading adopted (e.g., see [12, 13]).

The configuration examined in this note corresponds to what Weingarten [1] refers to as *hydrostatic pressure*. In the case of an open-ended cylinder (e.g., one closed by sliding pistons) there is, of course, no pressure-induced contribution to the pre-buckling axial stress resultant; this is termed *lateral pressure* in [1]. In terms of the expressions given in (1.2), the (underlined) pressure term drops from N_{xx} . It is instructive to contrast these two scenarios through the lens of the asymptotic approach adopted here. The comparison turns out to be relatively straightforward.

For the lateral pressure case, the dispersion function Λ is slightly modified: the underlined term in (2.1) must be replaced by $4\Pi p^2$. This alteration does not change the critical point of Λ , but it does affect the value of the minimum, which becomes independent of the applied pressure. Consequently, equation (3.5) must be replaced by $\lambda_0 = 1$, and the pressure now enters as an $\mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1/2})$ secondary effect. In particular, the expression of the correction term λ_2 in (3.7) is modified to

$$\lambda_2 = \left(k + \frac{1}{2}\right) \sqrt{\Pi}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots; \quad (5.1)$$

we note in passing that for $k = 0$ this result is consistent with the information provided by Reddy & Calladine in [2] (see their Table 1, first row, third column).

These simple observations account for most of the numerical findings reported in [1]. As a further example, Weingarten noted that the cross-sectional eigen-deformations appear more localised in the case of hydrostatic pressure. This can be readily explained by observing that the leading-order transverse displacement in both cases is governed by a parabolic cylinder function, implying that $G_0 \propto \exp(-\kappa Z^2)$, where $\kappa > 0$ depends on the loading condition. Letting κ_h and κ_ℓ denote the corresponding values for the hydrostatic and lateral pressure cases, respectively, one finds

$$\kappa_h := \frac{\sqrt{\Pi + 2}}{2\sqrt{2\Pi}} \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa_\ell := \frac{1}{2\sqrt{\Pi}}.$$

Both coefficients decrease monotonically as Π increases, indicating a weakening of localisation in the eigenmodes of the bifurcation system (1.5) with increasing pressure. However, since $\kappa_h > \kappa_\ell$, the spatial spreading of the buckled region noted by Weingarten is more pronounced in the lateral-pressure case than under hydrostatic loading. Numerical evidence supporting this assertion can be found in Figure 8 of reference [1].

Another item that deserves brief discussion concerns our earlier remarks vis-à-vis certain mathematical inconsistencies in the solution strategy proposed by Reddy & Calladine [2]. A detailed critique is beyond the scope of this short note, particularly because the buckling equations in that reference are formulated using a different scaling – based on the so-called ‘Batdorf parameter’ (see [13, 7]) – and are reduced to a single PDE for the transverse displacement. Despite these differences, their method also relied on a separation of variables for $w(x, \theta)$, akin to our formulation in (1.3), though the resulting ODE was used differently. Specifically, they assumed that a suitable approximation for the eigenmodes – both in the unpressurised and pressurised cases – could be represented by a Gaussian profile $\propto \exp(-\beta\theta^2)$, where $\beta > 0$ is a fitting parameter chosen to best match direct numerical

simulations from earlier studies [1, 5]. The other free parameter in their equations was an effective axial wavenumber, similar to our q . While this Gaussian assumption is reasonable for the pressurised case (as shown in our §3), it does not hold for the unpressurised scenario (cf. §3 of Part I and [4]).

It is noteworthy that their analysis correctly captured the $(h/R)^{2/3}$ scaling of the critical load correction (see Table 1 in [2], first row, second column). However, the numerical pre-factor they obtained was slightly overestimated, yielding an upper bound relative to numerically computed critical loads (see Figure 5 in the same reference). By contrast, our asymptotic analysis in [4] gives a coefficient $0.45226 \cdot [3(1 - \nu^2)]^{-1/3}$, which evaluates to approximately 0.3236 for $\nu = 0.3$, compared to the value 0.35 reported in [2] – a relative error of about 8%.

The usefulness of the Gaussian approximation in the unpressurised case is somewhat subtle. It stems from the fact that, in the limit $0 < (h/R) \ll 1$, the right branch of the corresponding neutral stability curve is asymptotically described by a parabolic cylinder function. As shown in Figure 9 of [4], this approximation remains reasonably accurate even near the global minimum of the curve. Consequently, there is a strong likelihood of obtaining a tight *upper bound* for the critical load by replacing the original fourth-order ODE with a Weber-Hermite-type equation (from a physical point of view this “approximation” results in a slight stiffening of the cylindrical shell). That said, it is important to recognise that the use of a Gaussian trial function in solving the buckling equation, as adopted in [2], is not without significant drawbacks. These originate in the fact that repeated differentiation of a Gaussian generates terms of the form $\theta^n \times \exp(-\beta\theta^2)$ (for $n = 1, 2, \dots$), thereby reintroducing the independent variable into the reduced equation once the exponential factor is divided out. This undermines the rationale for employing a separable assumed-form solution in the first place. To mitigate these issues, Reddy & Calladine restructure their bifurcation equation by isolating all basic-state-dependent terms on one side, and then approximate the cosine term in (1.2) using a second-order Maclaurin expansion in the azimuthal coordinate. On the other side of the equation, only even-order differential operators appear, whose action on the proposed Gaussian yields a bi-quadratic polynomial. The authors then argue that the fourth-order term can be neglected, allowing them to equate the coefficients of the constant and quadratic terms on both sides. From a mathematical point of view this approach is flawed, as the equality of two polynomials requires not only matching coefficients but also identical degrees. While the coefficient of the unmatched term may be small – as the authors verify on pages 648/649 – the resulting equation (21) in [2] remains problematic. The inconsistency arises primarily from the absence of a clearly defined asymptotic parameter and the fact that the azimuthal coordinate is left unscaled; there are other issues as well. In a future study we will demonstrate how some of these shortcomings can be addressed through a modified asymptotic framework, albeit one that can only deliver upper bounds for the critical buckling load.

A final aspect we wish to address concerns the regime where $\Pi = \mathcal{O}(\mu^{-s})$ for some fixed $s > 0$, so that $\Pi \ll \mathcal{O}(1)$. Based on the preceding discussion, one might expect the effect of pressure in this case to be rather weak, with the character of the instability resembling that of the unpressurised cylindrical shell in pure bending. This expectation is indeed confirmed, and we restrict our attention to two illustrative examples.

First, consider $\Pi = \mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1/3})$, i.e. $\Pi = \Pi_0 \mu^{-1/3}$ where $\Pi_0 = \mathcal{O}(1)$ is a known constant. Repeating the analysis of §3 in Part I (see also [4]), one finds that the critical load admits the asymptotic approximation

$$\lambda = 1 + \frac{\underline{\underline{\Pi}}}{2} + \lambda_2 \mu^{-2/3} + \dots, \quad (5.2a)$$

$$q = 2 + q_1 \mu^{-1/3} + \dots, \quad (5.2b)$$

where $q_1, \lambda_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ are determined by numerically minimising the function $q_1 \mapsto \lambda_2(q_1)$ arising from the reduced eigenvalue problem

$$\frac{d^4 G_0}{dZ^4} - (q_1 + \Pi_0) \frac{d^2 G_0}{dZ^2} + \left(\frac{q_1^2 - 8\lambda_2}{4} + Z^2 \right) G_0 = 0, \quad (5.3)$$

subject to the decay conditions $G_0, dG_0/dZ \rightarrow 0$ as $|Z| \rightarrow \infty$. We note in passing that the underlined term in (5.2a) is formally $\mathcal{O}(\mu^{-1/3})$, in contrast to the $\mathcal{O}(1)$ term appearing in (3.5).

Next, if the pressure is even smaller, say $\Pi = \mathcal{O}(\mu^{-2/3})$, then the asymptotic structure (5.2) is slightly modified. The second equation remains unchanged, while the first becomes $\lambda = 1 + \lambda_2 \mu^{-2/3} + \dots$, with λ_2 again obtained via minimisation of $q_1 \rightarrow \lambda_2(q_1)$, but now governed by the differential equation

$$\frac{d^4 G_0}{dZ^4} - q_1 \frac{d^2 G_0}{dZ^2} + \left(\frac{q_1^2 - 8\lambda_2}{4} + \Pi_0 + Z^2 \right) G_0 = 0, \quad (5.4)$$

where $\Pi = \Pi_0 \mu^{-2/3}$ and $\Pi_0 = \mathcal{O}(1)$ is prescribed.

The asymptotic structure outlined above is corroborated by direct numerical simulations, though the corresponding results are not presented here for the sake of brevity.

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